

**OPPORTUNITIES OF STUDYING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE
IN THE DEVELOPMENT CITIZENSHIP COMPETENCIES
OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS**

Zemlina Yuliya Vyacheslavovna

State Specialized School No. 51, Tashkent city, PhD

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Аннотация. *Статья раскрывает преимущества изучения иностранного языка в качестве средства постепенного формирования нравственных компетенций, в том числе гражданственных и патриотических, разъясняются методы, применяемые в качестве основных для реализации воспитательных целей урока через урок иностранного языка.*

Ключевые слова: *урок, иностранный язык, воспитательные цели, нравственность, гражданственность.*

Аннотация. *Мақолада ахлоқий, шу жумладан фуқаролик ва ватанпарварлик қобилиятларини босқичма-босқич ривожлантириши воситаси сифатида чет тилини ўрганишининг афзалликлари очиб берилган, чет тили дарси орқали дарсининг тарбиявий мақсадларини амалга оширишининг асосий усуллари сифатида қўлланиладиган усуллар тушунтирилган.*

Калим сўзлар: *дарс, чет тили, тарбиявий мақсадлар, ахлоқ, фуқаролик.*

Abstract. *The article reveals the advantages of learning a foreign language as a means of gradually developing moral competencies, including civic and patriotic ones, and explains the methods used as the main ones for realizing the educational goals of the lesson through a foreign language lesson.*

Keywords: *lesson, foreign language, educational goals, morality, citizenship.*

As it's known, primary school is designed not only to form basic knowledge competencies among primary school students, but also to cultivate the basis for nurturing the culture of the future young person [1]. Problems of education, including the development of patriotic feelings, in elementary school mainly fall on the shoulders of the class teacher. However, the intra-subject approach, which justifies the implementation of the educational goals of the lesson, can be applied in any lesson. This principle applies not only to humanities subjects: integrated methods can make it possible to address issues of morality in science subjects, physical education, and other sciences that seem to be unrelated to this issue.

However, the role of linguistic subjects in the formation of morality (and citizenship is considered as part of it) cannot be underestimated. This fact depends on a number of factors:

- The republic has achieved success in many areas, but the most important thing is the preservation of peace, stability and interethnic harmony; the national cultural centers of Uzbekistan contribute to this. The Government of the Republic provides all possible support for the comprehensive development of culture, and any language, being a direct part of culture, developing, demanding attention, can in turn “repay in kind” - help the development of a harmoniously developed personality, educating its students in the idea of patriotism.

- Any language develops a culture of communication, and the subject of this culture can also be the topic of nurturing love for the Motherland. It is necessary to make extensive use of such language opportunities.

- Any language allows you to look into history. The roots of languages are united by many common aspects. This fact makes it possible to reason in class, compare, and do typological analysis, which can also be used for the purpose of cultivating patriotic feelings.

Thus, it turns out that the language has the ability to carry out educational actions from three current positions: past, present and future. A look into history, conclusions, results - the past; communication culture – modernity; the relationship between different cultures – is an apt step towards the development of promising relations in the future.

What methods can be used to educate young people in the idea of patriotism?

Let's start with traditional methods known to every teacher and easily applied in the classroom.

- * The use of local history texts creates a sense of pride in the achievements of our Motherland, in the history of our region, and fosters a respectful attitude towards national culture, language, traditions and customs.

- * Texts based on the biography of great persons allow to develop interest in the history of Uzbekistan, compare the cultures of different countries with our country in different eras, help to conduct a typological analysis of culture and history, foster a sense of desire for the same achievements, allow to set positive goals in life, thereby promoting a country to a high level.

- * Geographical texts - in addition to the main goal - environmental education - aim to introduce the natural features of our region, and therefore teach us to strive to do everything possible to preserve these riches for the benefit of the Motherland, to contribute to the development of scientific and technological achievements that ensure long-term stability in this area.

These types of texts can be used in a foreign language lessons in the form of small messages by the teacher or students as an option for updating knowledge, an element of an organizational moment, five minutes of political information before the start of the lesson, as well as in the form of traditional works - dictations (auditory, visual, picture, deformed, letter etc.), presentations (uncomplicated and creative - with elements of an essay), essays (based on a picture, descriptions, reasoning, etc.).

- At the same time, proverbs and sayings of the peoples of the world, aphorisms, and statements of outstanding figures of culture, science, and art can be used for this work.

- Interdisciplinary connections and integrated lessons today are a direct element of teacher preparation for a lesson. Using samples of poetry (literature), reporting facts about the development of historical events (history), counting the number of sounds in phonetic analysis (arithmetic), drawing up pyramids of knowledge (geometry), describing geographical objects (natural history), conversations about behavior (ethics), physical education (physical education), working with paper (technology) - all these and other details of the lesson can have the property of educating students.

As can be seen from the types of work already listed, this topic provides a huge selection of tasks that can be easily applied in every lesson.

In addition to traditional options, currently there are a lot of innovative methods that, unlike those listed above, enable the student to be a direct performer of actions, to be a subject and not an object of the learning process. Such technologies can also be used as an educational tool.

- * Tests, that have already become traditional, include at least a few sentences about the Motherland. (eg. In this sentence determine the subject: Autumn has come to Uzbekistan. A) Autumn B) has come C) Uzbekistan).

* Also widespread and easily used is a cluster. In its variants, you can give a central word related to the Motherland; outgoing words that are associated only, for example, with the culture of Uzbekistan; limit the cluster to 12 words - a number that is a symbol of perfection for the Republic, etc. As cluster analogues, you can use the “grapes” cluster, the “crystal” cluster, and also modify existing options.

Example of the “Grapes” cluster:

(goal: first to expand, then to narrow)

Topic: Nature of Uzbekistan

The central word: “nature”. We expand: water, air, earth. Then We are also expanding: fish, birds, animals, plants, people. We narrow it down: for example, habitats: reservoirs, forests, house. We further narrow it down to one final word, for example, according to logic, all three of the above words can be combined by the word “life”, or the word “Motherland”. Next, it is necessary to analyze this scheme and prove that the central word is directly related to the final word: nature - Motherland or nature - life, etc.

* cinquain can also be used as an element of education. When and how should you use cinquain? Due to the fact that the shape of cinquain is a triangle, and in psychology it has been proven that it is this figure that can arouse the greatest interest in a student as the most memorable figure - cinquain should be used at the end of the lesson, at the final stage, when summing up. cinquain is able to summarize information and isolate its main features. Everything that was main in the lesson can be reflected in this element. For example,

Pict. 1.

A variant of applying cinquain as a method of addressing to the topic of culture.

At the grammatical level, it is also possible to compose a cinquain with elements of an appeal to the Motherland. The last 2 lines make it possible to use sentences in the form of statements, aphorisms, proverbs and stable phrases, which can be fully associated with the culture and customs of Uzbekistan. That is, you can take the grammatical beginning as the central word, for example: “adjective”, and in the final lines use sentences about the Motherland with this part of speech.

*The next method is the “fishbone” method.

An example of using this method in a foreign language lesson with elements of addressing the Motherland: The central link is the word “adjective”. The task can be used as a reinforcing element when generalizing knowledge about the adjective. The word "adjective" is placed on the main body of the fish. On the upper bones there are criteria (signs) of the adjective: form, gender, number, case. Goal: select examples of adjectives based on these characteristics; the words must be relevant to our city. Result:

Tashkent is associated with the following adjectives: beautiful, clean, ancient, sunny.

* Continuing the theme of environmental education, we can suggest the “Magic Carpet” technique. This method is closely intertwined with the already well-known “Zigzag” technology, which teachers often turn to during reading lessons, especially extracurricular reading, natural history, and ethics.

This method can be used to devote most of the lesson and can be used to reinforce the material.

Lesson steps:

1. The class is divided into 5 groups.
2. A large text with additional information on the topic “Bukhara deer” is divided into 5 parts.
3. Each part is given separately to groups for five minutes to read.
4. After reading, team representatives change places using the “Zigzag” method, sharing information about what they read group with group.

This technology is used to obtain large-scale information, it easier processing.

5. Teams return to their places. A grammar task is given.

Make up sentences on the topic “Bukhara deer” using 2 nouns in sentences.

6. Each team receives sheets of colored paper. There is a note on the board that each case corresponds to a certain color of paper. Students write each sentence in a specific color. Then the strips of paper are glued to paper.

7. Protection of the “magic carpet”. Team representatives take out the resulting carpets. Suggestions are read out. Already by the colors used most often in works, students can draw a conclusion about which cases are most often used in our speech.

8. Summing up the results of the work: the team whose carpet is the brightest, that is, words of all cases were used in it, wins. The teacher will definitely ask: “What new did you learn today? What does today's lesson teach? How can you help the nature of our region? etc.

Of course, these examples of technologies represent a tiny part of the endless sea of methods that a teacher can apply today in his lesson with the aim of educating a harmoniously developed personality, a respectable citizen of our country who loves his motherland.

To summarize all the facts, mentioned above, We would like to emphasize once again that a foreign language as an academic subject is capable of not only involving students in the learning process, but also educating our youth according to existing ethical standards, affecting all aspects of education. Therefore, education in the classroom should become part of teaching, and the teacher needs to develop the habit of using methods that contribute to the achievement of this goal

Education of patriotism is a tireless work to create in schoolchildren a sense of pride in their Motherland and their people, respect for its great achievements and worthy pages of the past, and the role of a foreign language in this regard cannot be overestimated.

REFERENCES

1. Puspitasari D. et al. How do primary school English textbooks teach moral values? A critical discourse analysis //Studies in Educational Evaluation. – 2021. – T. 70. – C. 101044.

2. From the congratulatory report of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at a gala event dedicated to the 25th anniversary of the International Cultural Center of Uzbekistan on January 25, 2017 // <https://uzreport.news/culture/v-uzbekistane-otmetili-25-letie-internatsionalnogo-kulturnogo-tsentra>